

PERCEIVED PARENTING STYLES AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG IRANIAN BOY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of present study examined the association between perceived parenting styles and emotional intelligence in Iranian boy students. The sample size was 188 boy students (age from 16 to 19) were chosen by a multi-stage cluster sampling method. For gathering data, students filled out Parental bonding instrument (PBI), and Assessing Emotions Scale (AES). To analyze the data, Pearson correlation coefficient and multivariate regression analysis were used. The findings revealed there were positive associations between affectionate constraint parenting style, and optimal parenting style with high ability of emotional intelligence, and negative associations existed between affectionless control style and neglectful parenting style with high ability of emotional intelligence. The affectionate constraint parenting style was a powerful predictor of high ability of emotional intelligence, and neglectful parenting style was a plausible predictor of low ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents.

Keywords: Perceived Parenting Styles, Depression, Iranian, Students

INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence as one of the important factors play an important role in mental health. Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso (2004) defined emotional intelligence as a kind of social intelligence, includes the capability of monitoring one's emotions and other's emotions, and manipulating the information for managing one's thoughts and actions, and regulating emotion in self and others, and utilizing suitable emotions for solving actively and effectively daily difficulties and obstacles. Noorbakhsh, Besharat, and Zarei (2010) concluded individuals high in emotional intelligence have more successful performances than individuals low in emotional intelligences. Schutte et al. (2001) revealed individuals with high ability of emotional intelligence reported greater empathy, self-control, cooperative responses, kindly relationships, and marital satisfaction than individuals with low ability of emotional intelligence. Several studies have revealed that emotional intelligence is a powerful predictor of success in different aspects, such as life skills, mental health, academic achievement (Bastian, Burns, & Nettelbeck, 2005; Fernandez-Berrocal, Alcaide, Extremera, & Pizarro, 2006; Goldenberg, Matheson, & Mantler, 2006; Lloyd, Malek-Ahmadi, Barclay, Fernandez, & Chartrand, 2012). Bar-On (2000) stated that emotional intelligence often expanded and developed by training. In the same vein, Other Studies have shown that emotional intelligence is an ability that can be learned (Clyne & Blampied, 2004; Dasborough & Ashkanasy, 2003; Hein, 2005; Kotsou, Nelis, Grégoire, & Mikolajczak, 2011). One of the benefits of emotional intelligence than IQ is the acquisition, because individuals can learn, develop, and improve their emotional intelligence (Brown & Moshavi, 2005; Harms & Credé, 2010; Metz, 2004). Among the social factors influencing on emotional intelligence, parents play a key role in emotional intelligence training (Fonte, 2009; Hsieh, 2006), because they play an important role in fostering of children. Several studies have revealed that a significant association existed between high ability of emotional intelligence

with perceived care and supportive parent-ing style (Lopes et al., 2004; Lopes, Salovey, & Straus, 2003). In another study, Fonte (2009) showed that a positive association existed between authoritative parenting style and high ability of emotional intelligence in children, and a negative association existed between permissive parenting style with the ability of emotional intelligence in children. Asghari and Besharat (2011) found that a significant association existed between perceived warmth parenting style and high ability of emotional intelligence in Iranian students. Perceived parenting styles defined as an opinion of adolescences or children about styles of parental behaviors during their childhood. According to the definition, assessment of children about parental behaviors is important. There are two types of perceived parenting styles: care, and overproduction. Several studies have revealed that rejective and overprotective parenting styles significantly associated with emotional intelligence in their children (Fonte, 2009; Lopes et al., 2004). Perceived parenting styles defined as a perception of adolescents or children about styles of parental behaviors during the childhood. Based on the definition, assessment of children about parental behavior is important. Theoretical model of perceived parenting styles consists of care, and overproduction (Gordon Parker, 1983). The studies have concluded that rejective, and overprotective parenting styles significantly associated with depression in children (Bemporad & Romano, 1992). Children with overprotective parenting style and extreme control lead to dependency to the parents, and they could not be autonomous and overcome to their problems. Therefore, lack of care and overprotective parental styles are likely influence on self-image and susceptibility to depression, low self-esteem, and low ability of emotional intelligence (Thammawijaya, 2012).

Current research efforts to study between perceived parenting styles and emotional intelligence in Iranian boy students, and what kinds of perceived parenting styles predict low or high ability of emotional intelligence in Iranian boy students.

METHOD

Participants and Procedure

The sample comprised of 188 high school students, and their ages were from 16 to 19 years old ($M= 17.1$, $SD=. 93$). A random cluster sampling was used. There were fifty-five high schools in the Ministry of Education, Tehran, 11 region. Six schools were chosen randomly, and one class was chosen from every school. I got permission from Ministry of Education for gathering data. All students in these classes were chosen as participants for this study. Data collected during one of the regularly scheduled classes. They completed questionnaires, included Parental bonding instrument (PBI) which was separately completed by students for their fathers and mothers, and The Schutte Emotional Intelligence Scale and Demographic questions were completed.

Instruments

Parental bonding instrument (PBI) created by G. Parker, Tupling, and Brown (1979) is a self-report questionnaire about retroactive experiences of children about parental behaviors during the childhood period. This questionnaire comprises of 25 items assess an adolescent's view about parenting styles in two aspects. One of them is care with 12 items, and it evaluates warmth and affection; another one is overprotective parenting style with 13 items evaluate the opinion of children about the control parenting styles. This questionnaire filled out by adolescents separately for mothers and fathers. All questions are in 4-point Likert scales from 0 (Very unlike), 1 (moderately unlike), 2 (moderately like) and 3 (Very like). For example, this item is representative of overprotective parenting style” Was overprotective of

me” and this item is representative of care parenting style” Appeared to understand my problems and worries.” In base on PBI scores, parenting styles were divided into four levels, affectionate constraint (high in care and protection), Optimal parenting (high care and low protection), affectionless control (high protection and low care), and neglectful parenting (low in care and protection). The studies reported good concurrent validity and reliability (Herz & Gullone, 1999; G. Parker et al., 1979; Wilhelm, Niven, Parker, & Hadzi-Pavlovic, 2005). In the present study, the reliability of care, and overproduction were α : .79 and α : .75, respectively.

Assessing Emotions Scale (AES) is created by Schutte base on the model of emotional intelligence created by Mayer and Salovey (1993). This self-report questionnaire comprises of 33 items assess characteristics of emotional intelligence in self and others. All questions are in 5-point Likert scales from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Total scale scores calculate by reverse coding items 5, 28 and 33, and then summing all items. The total score is from 33 to 165. A higher score indicates the higher ability of emotional intelligence and conversely. AES divided into three sub scales, Appraisal of Emotions, Use of Emotions and Regulation of Emotions. Schutte et al. (1998) suggested using the total scores of AES rather than scores of sub scales. The AES had a good internal consistency with alpha: .90 and test-retest reliability was .87 (Schutte et al., 1998). Several studies have revealed that this questionnaire had a powerful convergent and divergent validity (Bastian et al., 2005; Brackett & Mayer, 2003). At the false form of this scale (Besharat, 2007) alpha ‘s chronbach in a 135 students was 0.88, which showed a good internal consistency. In the current study, the reliability was α : .88. Based on their AES scores, adolescents in this study were divided into two levels of emotional intelligence – low ability of emotional intelligence (1 to 82.5), high ability of emotional intelligence (Up to 82.5).

Demographic survey

Demographic information was collected to measure different features of an individual’s background. Participants completed a demographic survey about their age, educational level, and family structure.

RESULTS

Simple frequency analysis in SPSS 20 was used to present demographic information, including education levels, family structure, age, and depression in Table 1. As it can be seen from the table 1, almost half (53.2%) of all adolescents reported high levels of emotional intelligence and nearly half (46.8%) of all adolescents reported low levels of emotional intelligence. Nearly Two-thirds (79.80%) of adolescents reported their parents are alive, and (12.20%) of adolescents were living with a single parent, and (8%) of adolescents reported their parents divorced. Participants equally were in junior, sophomore, and senior levels nearly (33%). The ages of participants were from 16 to 18 years old equally by (32%) except for 19 years old (6%). Pearson's correlation and multivariate regression used to analyze data.

Table1. Demographic information, including education levels, family structure, age, and depression

	EI		Family Structure			Education levels			Age			
	High	Low	Single	Alive	Div	Junior	Sop	Senior	16	17	18	19
n	100	88	23	15	15	62	62	64	60	60	56	12
%	53.2	46.8	12.2	79.8	8	33	33	34	31.9	31.9	29.8	6.4

n: Number, Div: Divorced, Sop: Sophomore

As can be seen from table 2. Negative correlations existed between low ability of emotional intelligence and paternal affectionate constraint style and paternal optimal parenting style, and positive association existed between paternal affectionless control, and paternal neglectful parenting style with low ability of emotional intelligence. There were positive associations between high ability of emotional intelligence with paternal affectionate constraint, and paternal optimal parenting style, and a negative association existed between high ability of emotional intelligence with paternal affectionless control style, and paternal neglectful parenting. These results are significant at $p < 0.01$ levels.

Table 2. Pearson correlation between parenting styles and Emotional intelligence

	Paternal parenting styles				Maternal parenting styles			
	AC	OP	ALC	NP	AC	OP	ALC	NP
LowEI1	-.554**	-.021**	.367**	.380**	-.621**	-.412**	.451**	.481**
highEI1	.564**	.026**	-.387**	-.395**	.632**	.321**	-.481**	-.512**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Affectionate Constraint: AC, Optimal Parenting: OP, Affectionless control: ALC, Neglectful Parenting: NP

In regard of maternal parenting styles with adolescence's emotional intelligence, the table.2 shows that negative associations existed between low ability of emotional intelligence with maternal affectionate constraint and maternal optimal parenting, and positive associations existed between low ability of emotional intelligence with maternal affectionless control and maternal neglectful parenting. There were positive associations between high ability of emotional intelligence with maternal affectionate constraint and maternal optimal parenting, and there were negative associations existed between high ability of emotional intelligence with maternal affectionless control and maternal neglectful parenting styles.

It is apparent in Table. 3, that paternal neglectful parenting style was the greatest predictor of low ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents (.48). In addition, the paternal affectionate constraint negatively predicted low ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents (-.052). The results showed the paternal Affectionless control style, and the paternal neglectful parenting style negatively predicted high ability of emotional intelligence with (-.44), and (-.48) in adolescents, respectively. In addition, paternal affectionate constraint positively predicted high ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents (.41).

Table 3. Results of multivariate regression analysis of perceived parenting styles to predict Emotional intelligence

Paternal	B	Beta	F(3,184)	Adjusted R square	Maternal	B	Beta	F(3,184)	Adjusted R square
AC	-.412a	-.378a			AC	-.406a	-.372a		
ALC	.447a	.328a	51.055 ^a	.445 ^a	ALC	.467a	.332a	54.223 ^a	.461 ^a
NP	.481a	.327a			NP	.487a	.353a		
AC	.412b	.378b			AC	.471b	.392b		
ALC	-.447b	-.327b	55.021 ^b	.472 ^b	ALC	-.482b	-.345b	54.882 ^b	0.466 ^b
NP	-.481b	-.328b			NP	-.487b	-.352b		

a. Dependent Variable: Low levels EI,

b. Dependent Variable: high levels of EI

Affectionate Constraint: AC, Optimal Parenting: OP

Affectionless control: ALC, Neglectful Parenting: NP

In addition, the results showed that maternal neglectful parenting style, and maternal affectionless control style were powerful predictors of low ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents (.47) and (.49) respectively. Maternal affectionate constraint style negatively

predicted low ability of emotional intelligence (-.41) in adolescents. Maternal neglectful parenting style and maternal affectionless control parenting style negatively predicted high ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents (-.48), and (-.49), respectively. Maternal affectionate constraint parenting style positively predicted high ability of emotional intelligence by (.47) in adolescents. These results were significant at $p < 0.01$ levels.

DISCUSSION

Returning to the questions posed at the beginning of this study, it is now possible to state that affectionate constraint parenting style and optimal parenting style were positively associated with high ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents, and affectionless control parenting style, and neglectful parenting styles were negatively associated with high ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents. Also, paternal and maternal neglectful parenting styles were the highest predictors of low ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents, and paternal and maternal affectionate constraint styles were the highest predictors of high ability of emotional intelligence in adolescents. These findings are consistent with previous studies (Asghari & Besharat, 2011; Delale, Taksic, & Ivcevic, 2007; Fonte, 2009; Hsieh, 2006; Nastas & Sala, 2012; Thammawijaya, 2012).

The current findings add to the body of literature on emotional intelligence, and the vital role of parenting style in the development of emotional intelligence in adolescents and children. The findings of this study are expected, because the root of emotional intelligence is affection, and affectionate constraint parenting style trains regulation, utilization, and appraisal emotions in adolescents and children. According to the findings, it appears that early parents-child relationship is crucial, and parents would have the affectionate parenting style with children, and parents would care the basic needs of children, and in the childhood period, they allow them the autonomy for growing self-confidence, self-regulation and emotional integrity.

According to the social learning Theory, parents are the pattern for children (Gottman, 2001). If parents had favorable emotional awareness, their children would learn emotional regulation from them; and they could express favorable emotions for solving the problems in their lives, eventually; parents have the children with high ability of emotional awareness.

Several important limits need to be considered. First, data for this study were collected by using self-report instruments. These self-report instruments might produce exaggerated optimal responses; therefore, it is better other researchers use other suitable methods for assessing EI, such as direct observation, peer or family member's assessment. Second, the subjects of the study belong to the high school students; therefore, the results cannot be generalized to girls or boys, who study at different levels of education.

The findings of this study have several important implications for clinicians, counselors in schools, universities, and mental health centers for training emotional intelligence in adolescences. Additionally, the findings from this study can be fruitful for parents and family members to nurture a generation with greater emotional intelligence and mental health. Also, it is recommended that through speech makes parents aware of the consequence of negative parenting styles on children.

It is recommended that further studies be undertaken in the following areas: First, need to further researches about family structure, and parenting styles with emotional intelligence in adolescents. Second, future studies could be done as a comparative study between individuals with high ability of emotional intelligence, and low ability of emotional intelligence about their mental health and other features that play important roles in their emotional intelligence.

Also, in regard to the urbanization characteristics and the study was done in Tehran city. It seems the results would be different in the village. Therefore, I suggest that the future study could be done in the village, because of the social and cultural differences between city and village. Lastly, need to research on the association between parental emotional intelligence with the emotional intelligence of children.

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